

Integrated pest management—diseases

Seed sprout extracts for control of rice tungro disease (RTD)

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Some botanical extracts reportedly reduce the infection of plant viruses. We tested the effect of seed sprout extracts of leguminous plants (see table) in reducing RTD infection.

We soaked the seeds in water for 72 h. We macerated the sprouts after diluting the extract with distilled water to get a 10% concentration (wt/vol). Extracts were sprayed at 5 and 10% concentration, on twenty-five 15-d-old CO 43 rice seedlings per treatment. Teepol was added to the spray at 1 ml/liter. Plants sprayed with distilled water and teepol served as control.

Rice plants were infested 24 h after treatment with two viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* Distant per plant. Treatments were arranged in a completely randomized design. We calculated the percentage of infected plants after infection symptoms developed and the percent reduction in infection over the control (see table).

Effect of seed sprout extracts on tungro infection in CO 43 rice plants.

Plant source of extract	Variety	Concentration (%)	Infection (%)	Reduction (%) over control ^a
Pigeonpea <i>Cajanus cajan</i> (L.) Millsp.	CO 5	5	12	84.3 (66.65)
		10	8	89.5 (71.09)
Mungbean <i>Vigna radiata</i> (L.) Wilczek	CO 5	5	16	79.0 (62.73)
		10	12	84.3 (66.65)
Black gram <i>Vigna mungo</i> (L.) Hepper	CoBG 305	5	20	73.8 (59.21)
		10	12	84.3 (66.65)
Cowpea <i>Vigna unguiculata</i> (L.) Walp.	CO 4	5	20	73.8 (59.21)
		10	16	79.0 (62.73)
Lablab <i>Lablab purpureus</i> (L.) Sweet var <i>puspureus</i>	CO 9 (vegetable type)	5	36	55.0 (47.86)
		10	24	68.6 (55.92)
Lablab <i>Lablab purpureus</i> (L.) Sweet var	CO 10 (grain type)	5	32	60.0 (50.78)
		10	20	73.8 (59.21)
Soybean <i>Glycine max</i> L.	CO 1	5	36	55.0 (47.86)
		10	20	73.8 (59.21)
Horse gram <i>Vigna unguiculata</i> (L.) Walp. subsp. <i>unguiculata</i>	CO 1	5	52	32.9 (35.10)
		10	48	37.1 (37.52)
Bengal gram <i>Cicer arietinum</i> L.	CO 3	5	36	55.0 (47.86)
		10	24	68.6 (55.92)
Alfalfa <i>Medicago sativa</i> L.	CO 1	5	24	68.6 (55.92)
		10	20	73.8 (59.21)
<i>Prosopis cineraria</i> (L.) Durce	<i>b</i>	5	60	21.4 (27.56)
		10	48	37.1 (37.52)
Subabul <i>Leucaena leucocephala</i> (Lam.) de Wit.	CO 1	5	32	60.0 (50.78)
		10	28	63.3 (52.71)
<i>Sesbania rostrata</i> Brem & Oberm.	<i>b</i>	5	24	68.6 (55.92)
		10	20	73.8 (59.21)
Control (water spray)		–	76	– (0.57)
LSD (P = 0.05)		4.8		

^aValues in parentheses are sine transformed ones. ^bVarietal designation is not available.

Extract from pigeonpea, mungbean, and black gram at 10% concentrations reduced infection 84.3–89.5% over the control. Extracts at 10% concentration were more effective than those at 5%.

Extracts from other plants also reduced infection by 21.4–79%. Experiments are being conducted to find how different fractions of the extracts affect infection. □

Survey of Pakistan's rice crop for bakanae disease

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We randomly surveyed about 200 nearly mature ricefields in 22 localities in Pakistan for bakanae disease from Oct to Nov 1990. Field identification was based on plant appearance. Typical symptoms were elongated plants. The disease was confirmed in the laboratory by isolating the pathogen *Fusarium moniliforme* Sheld from diseased plants and back-inoculating it to rice.

Disease incidence percentage—the number of infected plants per 200 plants

Bakanae disease incidence in rice in Pakistan, 1990.

Locality	Fields surveyed (no.)	Disease incidence (%/field)		Locality	Fields surveyed (no.)	Disease incidence (%/field)	
		Range	Average			Range	Average
Bannu	3	1.3 – 9.2	4.1	Nankana Sahib	10	1.0 – 2.7	1.3
Daska	7	1.3 – 2.1	1.5	Narowal	9	0.7 – 7.3	5.2
D.G. Khan	4	–	–	Okara	11	3.0 – 11.1	9.2
Faisalabad	21	–	–	Sahiwal	12	1.3 – 3.9	2.1
Gujranwala	16	1.9 – 21.2	3.9	Saidu	4	–	–
Hafizabad	4	3.1 – 17.7	15.1	Sawat	4	–	–
Jaranwala	19	2.1 – 7.2	4.7	Sheikhupura	12	2.1 – 63	12.2
Kambar	3	–	–	Sialkot	13	7.0 – 43.1	21.3
Kasur	18	3.9 – 7.3	5.5	Sumandri	9	–	–
Khuzdar	3	–	–	Umarkot	3	3.1 – 11.2	7.1
				Vihari	10	2.2 – 3.1	2.5

in each field—ranged from no symptoms in some areas to 63% around Sheikhupura (see table). The results

suggest bakanae disease is becoming significant in Pakistan's ricefields. □